

Geostructural Investigation of the Lugiin Gol Area Using Optical and Microwave Remote Sensing

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Abstract: This study aims to investigate the geostructural characteristics of the Lugiin Gol area through the integration of optical and microwave remote sensing (RS) data. To achieve this objective, a combination of image enhancement techniques was applied to multisource RS datasets to improve the discrimination of lithological units and geostructures. The results demonstrate that synthetic aperture radar (SAR) data are particularly effective for detecting structural features, such as faults and lineaments, whereas multispectral imagery provides valuable information for identifying lithological variability and alteration zones based on spectral reflectance characteristics. Image enhancement approaches, including false color composite (FCC) generation, contrast stretching, band ratioing, and spatial filtering, significantly improved the visual interpretation and delineation of geological features. In addition, advanced transformation techniques, namely principal component analysis (PCA) and minimum noise fraction (MNF), were employed to extract supplementary spatial and spectral information from the datasets. Among these methods, the MNF transformation demonstrated superior performance in noise reduction and the enhancement of geological patterns. The integrated analysis enabled clearer identification of geostructural features, lithological boundaries, and possible subsurface intrusions within the study area. Overall, the findings indicate that the integration of optical and microwave RS data, combined with advanced image processing techniques, provides a reliable and effective framework for comprehensive geostructural investigation, while also supporting environmental assessment, land-use planning, and informed decision-making in geologically complex regions.

Keywords: optical; SAR; geostructure; analysis; Lugiin Gol.

1 Introduction

Over the years, RS has been successfully applied across diverse geoscience disciplines. It plays a critical role in geological interpretation, mineral and hydrocarbon exploration, geomorphological mapping, and structural analysis by enabling synoptic, repeatable, and cost-effective data acquisition over large and often inaccessible areas (Sabins and Ellis 2020). In recent years, the scope of RS applications has expanded significantly to include environmental monitoring, natural resource management, and sustainable development planning, thereby supporting evidence-based decision-making and policy

formulation (Wulder et al. 2019, Zhang et al. 2024, Portela et al. 2025).

Technological advancements in both optical and microwave sensing systems have substantially improved the capabilities of RS for geoscientific investigations (Tompolidi et al. 2025). The rapid expansion of large, openly accessible satellite image archives, particularly from missions such as Sentinel and Landsat, has enabled researchers to efficiently analyze extensive geological structures and environmental features and to generate high-quality scientific and decision-support products within relatively short timeframes (Amarsaikhan et al. 2022, Carvalho et al. 2025). Meanwhile, the integration of advanced multi-sensor data, together with continuous improvements in image processing and analytical algorithms, has further strengthened the accuracy and reliability of RS-based investigations and applications (Jensch et al. 2025).

The aim of this study is to investigate, for the first time, the geostructural characteristics of the Lugiin Gol area in Mongolia for the first time using integrated optical and SAR datasets and to demonstrate how the derived results can support sustainable development planning. For this purpose, Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 multispectral images acquired in 2021 were utilized as the primary data sources.

A set of advanced RS techniques was applied for multisource data processing and interpretation, including image enhancement, spectral and textural analysis, feature extraction, and data fusion. The combined use of optical and radar information improves the reliability of geostructural interpretation and provides a stronger basis for environmental planning decisions.

2 Materials and methods

The Lugiin Gol area belongs to the arid, strongly continental natural environment of southeastern Mongolia. The area lies within the low- to mid-elevation Gobi upland zone and is characterized by low mountains and hilly terrain, dry channels and ephemeral valleys, and relatively level surfaces shaped by wind and water erosion (Dash et al. 2015). Permanent rivers are rare, and most drainage consists of seasonal channels and dry gullies.

The relief is generally open, with sparse vegetation cover, allowing good exposure of rock outcrops and providing favorable conditions for geological investigation. The site is distinguished by accumulations of Mesozoic sedimentary rocks, including sandstone, siltstone, clayey shale, and

conglomerates, as well as lacustrine–fluvial sedimentary sequences (Baatar et al. 2013). These deposits are interpreted as having formed in ancient continental lake and river basin environments (Hasegawa et al. 2012).

As data sources a combined use of multispectral Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-1 SAR images acquired on 12 May 2021 has been applied. In addition, a large scale geological map and some ground truth data were available. Figure 1 shows the test area illustrated in optical and radar image frames.

Figure 1. RS images of the test area: (a) Sentinel-2A image, (b) SAR image.

In our study, the following techniques were compared: multiple-point stretching, band ratios, convolution filtering of different sizes, low pass filtering of different sizes, Brovey transform, PCA, Gram-Schmidt fusion, wavelet-based method, and MNF transform. Detailed descriptions of these methods are given in Amarsaikhan and Ganchuluun (2015).

3 Results

Satellite RS has been widely applied for geostructural analysis and mapping in arid and semi-arid regions, yielding notable results over recent years. In this study, microwave imagery contributes information on geological structures, whereas multispectral imagery captures the spectral variability of different land surface features.

Initially, various FCC images were generated using different combinations of visible, near-infrared (NIR), and shortwave infrared (SWIR) bands. Combinations that integrated NIR and SWIR bands with at least one visible band generally produced satisfactory results. However, the most reliable representation of both spectral and spatial variability of geological features in the study area was achieved using multichannel Sentinel band combinations of 1-5-11 in RGB and 2-3-8a in RGB. In particular, the image enhanced through a multiple-point stretching technique yielded the best performance among all FCC outputs. In this approach, stretching was applied uniformly across the radiometric ranges of the histograms for all available bands. The resulting images are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The false color composite images of the test area: (a) Combination of 9-4-3 bands, (b) Combination of enhanced 11-4-3 bands.

The created FCC images effectively reveal geological structures and lithological variations. In particular, the northwest-trending fault and the associated limestone occurrence at its northwestern end provide valuable information for structural interpretation. Overall, the two images exhibit similar lithological and structural characteristics.

Band ratio analysis is widely regarded as an effective technique for lithological discrimination. In this study, a total of 15 band-ratio combinations were applied to enhance geological features, using all bands of Sentinel-2 along with two SAR channels. Of the selected band ratios, the following combinations were the most relevant for the geological analysis and enhancement of the spectral differences of relevant lithological units in the study area:

- RGB color composite of the band ratios: 11/12-4/3-11/7
- RGB color composite of the band ratios: 11/12-11/2-12/3
- IHS-enhanced RGB color composite of the band ratios: 12/9-11/8-9/5
- RGB color composite of the band ratios: 12/5-11/3-5/3.

Figure 3. Ratio images of the Khan Bogd area: (a) Combination of 11/12-4/3-11/7, (b) Combination of 11/12-11/2-12/3, (c) Combination of 12/9-11/8-9/5, (d) Combination of 12/5-11/3-5/3.

As could be seen from the ratios above, combinations involving SWIR bands produced superior results compared to other band combinations. The selected band ratio images are presented in Figure 3, where the ratio outputs clearly delineate geological structures and highlight spectral variations among different lithological units.

In these images, the Lugiin Gol alkaline granite body is more distinctly delineated, together with the surrounding hornfels zone. A lens-shaped body of ancient limestone is clearly identifiable to the north, while a small circular structure in the southeastern extension of the granite body may indicate the presence of a subsurface intrusion.

Over the years, convolution filtering has been widely employed for the spatial enhancement of geological structures. This approach includes various high-pass filters, such as Roberts, Sobel, and Laplacian type operators. In addition, low-pass filters of different kernel sizes have been extensively used for geological interpretation and analysis (Jargalan et al. 2022). In the present study, a total of 15 convolution-based and low-pass filters with varying window sizes were applied to both optical and SAR datasets. Among the outputs, the following 2 combinations demonstrated the better results in terms of the spatial and spectral enhancements of the geostructures in the study site:

- RGB composite: b_9 *highpass (3x3)- b_5 *highpass (5x5)- b_2 *lowpass (7x7)
- RGB composite: b_9 * highpass (3x3)- b_{11} *highpass (5x5)- b_{12} *highpass (5x5)

As seen from results of the convolution and low pass filtering, the outputs of spatial enhancement techniques obtained by the use of blue, red-edge, NIR, and SWIR bands of Sentinel-2 image illustrated the best results among the combinations. The images are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Results of the filtering: (a) Output 1, (b) Output 2.

The images shown in Figure 4, allow effective discrimination of geological structures and lithological units. In particular, a ring-shaped structure located in the southeastern part of the circular body appears more prominently in the images, suggesting the possible presence of another subsurface geological body or intrusion beneath the area.

Furthermore, the VV and VH polarization components of the SAR data and their average, processed using convolution-based filtering followed by a blurring effect filter, produced enhanced results for the detection and delineation of structural features (Figure 5).

To evaluate the spatial variability of structural features, MNF transformation and PCA were applied to both optical and microwave datasets. In both techniques, the resulting

Figure 6. Results of the PCA and MNF: a) Principal components of 1-2-3, b) Principal components of 3-4-6, c) Fraction outputs of 1-2-3, d) Fraction outputs of 4-5-2.

outputs consist of orthogonal components ordered by decreasing information content. These outputs were examined both individually and in combination. The most effective results (Figure 6) were achieved using the following combinations:

Figure 5. Enhanced Sentinel-1 image.

- RGB color composite of enhanced PCs 1-2-3 (Figure 6a)
- RGB color composite of PCs 3-4-6 (Figure 6b)
- RGB color composite of fraction outputs of 1-2-3 (Figure 6c)
- RGB color composite of fraction outputs of 4-5-2 (Figure 6d)

The PCA results indicate that, in addition to the combination of the first three PCs, accounting for more than 89% of the total variance, a combination of components 3-4-6, which explains less than 10% of the variance, also produced satisfactory results. This suggests that although the leading PCs capture most of the overall information, some of the lower-order components may still contain valuable features.

Similarly, the MNF analysis showed that, in the first case, the combination of fraction images 1-2-3 yielded the most reliable results, whereas in the second case, the combination 4-5-2 provided the best outcome. Other combinations of fraction images produced acceptable results, although they were not as effective as the selected combinations.

The results of the PCA and MNF transformations clearly delineate the circular structure of the Lugiin Gol body, however, the discrimination of other geological structures and lithological units remains relatively limited. Nevertheless, these transformations are effective for identifying topographic features, including gullies and terrain variations, thereby contributing to the interpretation of the geomorphological characteristics of the study area.

4 Discussion

The results demonstrate a strong complementarity between microwave and multispectral data for geostructural analysis, with SAR data effectively enhancing structural features and multispectral imagery capturing lithological variability. The integration of active and passive sensor data improves geostructural interpretation, particularly in arid and semi-arid environments where sparse vegetation cover and extensive surface exposure facilitate the identification of geological features (Lillesand et al. 2015). Hence, the synergistic use of the optical and radar datasets provides a reliable and scalable geospatial framework for regional geological investigation and structural interpretation.

The study further confirms that no single image processing technique is sufficient for comprehensive geological characterization. Rather, the combined application of FCCs, band ratioing, spatial filtering, PCA, and MNF transformations enables a more detailed and accurate representation of geological structures and lithological diversity. The consistent significance of SWIR bands throughout these analyses highlights their critical role in detecting mineralogical and surface variations associated with alteration processes and lithological changes (Van der Meer et al. 2012). This demonstrates the effectiveness of multispectral SWIR information for improving lithological mapping accuracy in geologically complex terrains.

The FCC and band ratio images effectively revealed geological structures and lithological variations within the study area, including the northwest-trending fault, the Lugiin Gol alkaline granite body, the surrounding hornfels zone, and ancient limestone occurrences. In addition, circular and ring-shaped structures identified in the southeastern extension of the granite body may indicate the presence of subsurface intrusions or concealed geological features. Filtered SAR imagery further improved the discrimination of structural and lithological units. The PCA and MNF transformations enhanced the visibility of the circular structure and geomorphological features such as gullies and terrain variations, with the MNF transformation demonstrating superior performance in

noise reduction and subtle geological feature enhancement.

Importantly, these methodological advances have direct implications for sustainable development and environmental planning. Improved delineation of lithological units and structural features supports more informed land-use decision-making, including infrastructure site selection, identification of geologically stable and hazard-prone zones, and assessment of mineral and groundwater resource potential (Gad and Kusky 2006).

Enhanced structural mapping of faults and fractures can contribute to groundwater exploration, geohazard assessment, and risk mitigation (Pour et al. 2016), while accurate lithological discrimination supports responsible resource utilization and minimizes environmental disturbance (Rajendran and Nasir 2014). Therefore, the integration of multisource data and advanced image processing techniques offers considerable potential for supporting sustainable geological investigation and regional planning in remote and geologically complex areas.

5 Conclusions

This study showed that the integration of optical and radar data provides a highly effective approach for geostructural analysis in arid and semi-arid environments. The complementary strengths of SAR and multispectral imagery enable improved detection of geostructures and enhanced characterization of lithological variability. False color composites incorporating NIR and SWIR bands significantly outperform visible-based combinations. Image enhancement and band ratio techniques, particularly those involving SWIR bands, further improve lithological discrimination and structural delineation due to their sensitivity to mineral composition. Spatial filtering proves valuable for highlighting faults and fractures without compromising spectral information, while PCA and MNF transformations reveal additional spatial variability. Notably, MNF effectively separates noise from meaningful signals, enhancing data interpretability. Overall, the integration of multi-sensor data and advanced analytical techniques provides high-quality geospatial information essential for evidence-based planning. These results support sustainable land management, environmental protection, and disaster risk reduction by enabling faster, more accurate, and cost-effective decision-making. Consequently, the approach presented in this study offers a practical framework for advancing sustainable development, particularly in data-scarce and environmentally sensitive regions.

6 References

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